

First International HPC workshop Deliverable D1.4

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 675191

About this document

Work package in charge: WP1: Governance, engagement and long-term sustainability

Actual delivery date for this deliverable: first draft version was delivered on PM7 (March 22, 2016). This last version has been finalised on 31 August 2016.

Dissemination level: PU (public)

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

This deliverable reports about the HPC (High-Performance Computing) workshop, which was held in Toulouse on April 6 and 7 in 2016. The report explains how this workshop relates, and builds upon, preceding workshops organized under the infrastructure project called IS-ENES2 (ENES stands for "European Network for Earth-System modelling"). The agenda of the workshop, as well as the list of attendees, are parts of this deliverable. Indications are also given about the way it is presently envisaged to exploit and further disseminate the results of the workshop.

2. Conclusion & Results

The workshop was considered by the community as a very helpful and productive meeting, needed by the various scientists to exchange about open issues, to confront new developments, to follow on earlier initiatives, to start new collaborations. The series will continue, with a major inflexion linked to the fact that meteorologists have now joined climate scientists to review the whole spectrum of HPC issues and discuss further development of advanced numerical models.

3. Project objectives

Given the themes covered by the workshop, this deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of almost all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes
Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	Yes
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	Yes
Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	Yes
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	Yes

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	No
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	Yes
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	Yes
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user	No

community.	
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	No
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

This report is about the 4th HPC (High-Performance Computing) workshop to be organized in Toulouse (France) on April 6 and 7, 2016. Although the 4th in a series of workshops which started under ENES (the "European Network for Earth System modelling") as early as 2011 in Lecce (IT), the present workshop is the first one to be organized under the ESIWACE umbrella and more specifically under Work package 1. ENES was also co-organizing the workshop, which has been prepared by an *ad hoc* scientific committee (SC) hired by the joint ENES-ESIWACE HPC Task Force.

Let's first recall that the first 3 HPC workshops took place on:

- (i) December, 14-16, 2011, in Lecce (IT), organized under Giovanni ALOISIO (CMCC);
- (ii) January 30 – February 1st, 2013, in Toulouse (FR), organized under Jean-Claude ANDRE (CERFACS), Sylvie JOUSSAUME (CNRS-LSCE) and Sophie VALCKE (CERFACS);
- (iii) March 17-19, 2014, in Hamburg (DE), organized under Joachim BIERCAMP (DKRZ).

A scientific paper, summarizing the main outcomes from the second (and also partly the first) workshop has been published in the Bulletin of the American Society (André *et al.*, 2014). This paper emphasizes the results of discussions between European scientists concerning issues such as performance inter-comparisons, models for petascale and exascale, data challenges, and internal and external community collaborations. It is also worth mentioning here the IS-ENES2 deliverable 3.1 entitled "Report on the technology tracking" published on June 5, 2015, which addresses the various avenues for developing climate models into the multi-petascale and exascale era. These preceding 3 workshops, as summarized by the above two papers, offered the basis on which the programme for the 4th workshop has been built by the *ad hoc* scientific committee (SC).

The SC is composed of (alphabetic order): Jean-Claude ANDRE (FR, CERFACS), Peter BAUER (ECMWF), Joachim BIERCAMP (DE, DKRZ), Reinhard BUDICH (DE, MPI-M), Uwe FLADRICH (SE, SMHI), Florian PRILL (DE, DWD), Kim SERRADELL (ES, BSC), Sophie VALCKE (FR, CERFACS).

The SC has been responsible for preparing the workshop, *i.e.* a number of tasks including

- (i) selection of topics to be addressed;
- (ii) selection of, and contact with, invited speakers;
- (iii) preparation and diffusion of a call for contributed papers;
- (iv) selection of contributions resulting from this call; and finally
- (v) establishment of the workshop programme.

The local organization in Toulouse has been the duty of Jean-Claude ANDRE and Sophie VALCKE (CERFACS), while Kerstin RONNEBERGER (DKRZ) has been involved with more general organizational matters.

The SC decided to organize 3 main sessions:

- (i) The European HPC ecosystem, to review the state-of-the-art in already active projects at various institutes;

- (ii) Innovative developments and today high-resolution models, including presentations from outside Europe (US and Japan);
- (iii) new paradigms in the fields of languages, standards, next-generation models, ...).

The final programme of the workshop was the following one:

Agenda			
08:30-09:00	Welcome coffee		
09:00- 09 :15	S. Joussaume, J. Biercamp & Organizing Committee	Opening and Welcome	
Day 1 09:15-12 :40	Session 1	The European HPC ecosystem	Chair : S. Valcke
09:15-09:35	S. Girona	BSC	EXDCI and its relation to Weather and Climate
09:35-09:55	A. Kennedy	EPCC	What PrACE can offer to Weather & Climate
09:55-10:15	J. Biercamp	DKRZ	The ESiWACE CoE
10:15-10:35	E. Audit	CEA	The EoCoE and its XIOS component
10:35-10:55	J. Labarta	BSC	The PoP CoE
10:55-11:25	Break		
11:25-11:45	P. Ruti	WMO	How to shape future met-services: a seamless perspective
11:45-12:05	P. Bauer	ECMWF	ESCAPE, Energy efficient SCalable Algorithms for weather Prediction at Exascale
12:05-12:25	M. Parsons	EPCC	NEXTGenIO Next Generation I/O for the Exascale
12:25-12:40	I. Kirchner	Freie Universität Berlin, Institute of Meteorology	A virtual laboratory for earth system studies
12:40-14:00	Lunch break		
Day 1 13:45-17:30	Session 2	Innovative developments (new dynamical cores, I/O, etc) and today high- resolution models	Chair: U. Fladrich
14:30-15:00	S. Nishizawa	RIKEN AICS (Japan)	High-resolution modelling and big data analysis at RIKEN AICS
15:00-15:30	V. Balaji	NOAA/GFDL	Recent advances in the GFDL Flexible Modeling System
15:30-16:00	Break		
16:00-16:20	P. Adamidis	DKRZ	HPC aspects of the ICON model and high-res simulations
16:20-16:40	C. Osuna	Meteo Swiss	STELLA and GridTools

16:40-17:00	P. Bauer	ECMWF	The hydrostatic and non-hydrostatic global model IFS/ARPEGE IFS/ARPEGE
17:00-17:15	R. Ford	SFTC Daresbury Laboratory	The Gungho dynamical core
17:15-17:30	A.K. Gupta	Uni Research Klima, Norway	Scalability of NorESM high-resolution model
17:30	End of Day 1		
20:00	Workshop dinner (Restaurant "L'Emulation Nautique")		
Day 2 09:00-09:45	Session 2 (follow-on)	Innovative developments (new dynamical cores, I/O's, ...) and today high-resolution models	Chair: F. Prill
09:00-09:15	K. Kulkarni	Juelich Supercomputing Center	The TerrSysMP terrestrial system modelling platform
09:15-09:30	C. Osuna	Swiss National Supercomputing Center	Status of ICON climate model port on GPUs
09:30-09:45	V. Balaji	NOAA/GFDL	CPMIP: Measurements of real model performance
Day 2 09:45-15:30	Session 3	New paradigms (languages, standards, next-generation models, ...)	Chair: R. Budich
09:45-10:15	M. Rezny	ARC Centre of Excellence in Climate System Science	On the paths to Exascale, will we be hungry?
10:15-10:45	S. McIntosh-Smith	Univ. Bristol	HPC future trends from a science perspective
10:45-11:05	M. Schulz	Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory & MPI-Forum	Software standards at the example of the Message Passing Interface MPI
11:05-11:35	Break		
11:35-11:55	P. Brown	Cray	Hardware, software, compilers - Future trends from a vendor's perspective
11:55-12:15	O. Oberst	IBM	Future storage, I/O, and data management
12:15-12:35	X. Vigouroux	ATOS	Why DKRZ asked the smart question? Why Bull expertise was key?
12:50-14:00	Lunch break		
14:00-14:15	A. McKinstry	Irish Centre for High-End Computing	HARMONIE, Hirlam-Aladin Research towards Mesoscale Operational NWP In Euromed
14:15-14:30	M. Acosta	Barcelona	Reproducibility of the Earth System

		Supercomputing Center	Models: A computational point of view
14:30-14:45	P. Dueben	Oxford University	The use of inexact hardware to improve weather and climate predictions
14:45-15:00	L. Kornblueh	Max Planck Institute for Meteorology	Is streaming an alternative for post-processing workflows?
15:00-15:15	J. Rood	ETH Zürich	CLAW: a tool providing performance portability across emerging computing architectures
15:15-15:30	P. Wohlschlegel	Allinea	Weather and climate models: preparing development workflow for exascale
15:30-16:00	Break		
Day 2 16:00-17:30	Round table		
16:00-16:20	A. Varghese	EU DG Connect (project officer of ESIWACE)	
16:20-17:30	General discussion	Co-chairs: M. Carter (Met O) <i>Community aspects</i> A. Kennedy (PrACE) <i>HPC-ecosystem aspects</i>	How the community would like to organize itself to address the challenges of the exascale?
Day 2 17:30-17:45	S. Jousaume & J. Biercamp	Closing	
Day 2 17:45	End of workshop		

76 persons participated to the 4th workshop. The attendance was mixed, with scientists, coming either from the climate modelling community or from the numerical weather prediction community, and with representatives from software and hardware vendors. It also included representatives from other projects, mostly supported by the European commission. The final list is as follows:

Name	Organisation	Speakers	Internal (int.) / External to the project
Jean-Claude André	Organizing committee		Int.
Sophie Valcke	CERFACS		Int.
Florian Prill	Deutscher Wetterdienst		Int.
Uwe Fladrich	SMHI		Int.
Kim Serradell	Barcelona Supercomputing Center		Int.

Joachim Biercamp	DKRZ		Int.
Peter Bauer	ECMWF		Int.
Reinhard Budich	MPI für Meteorologie		Int.
Kerstin Fieg	DKRZ		Int.
Graham Riley	University of Manchester		Int.
Eric Maisonnave	CERFACS		Int.
Øyvind Seland	Norwegian Meteorological Institute		Ext.
Thomas Ludwig	German Climate Computing Center		Int.
Christian Pagé	CERFACS		Int.
Yevhen Alforov	Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum		Int.
Wilco Hazeleger	Netherlands eScience Center		SAB
Rena Bakhshi	eScience Center/KNMI		Ext.
Mick Carter	Met Office		Int.
Marie-Alice Foujols	IPSL/CNRS		Int.
Alain Beuraud	Météo-France		Ext.
Sergi Girona	Barcelona Supercomputing Center		Int.
Giuseppe Congiu	Seagate		Int.
Rudolf Fischer	NEC Deutschland GmbH		Ext.
Sai Narasimhamurthy	Seagate		Int.
Roland Richter	SGI		Ext.
Cyril Mazaurec	AtoS		Int.
Xavier Vigouroux	AtoS HPC CEPP	Yes	Int.
Oriol Mula-Valls	Barcelona Supercomputing Center		Int.
Øyvind Seland	Norwegian Meteorological Institute		Ext.
Alok Kumar Gupta	Uni Research Klima, Norway	Yes	Int.
Ingo Kirchner	Freie Universität Berlin	Yes	Ext.
Stéphane Sénési	CNRM		Int.
Ketan Kulkarni	Juelich Supercomputing Centre	Yes	Ext.
Luis Kornblueh	Max Planck Institute for Meteorology	Yes	Int.
Philip Brown	Cray Inc.	Yes	Ext.
Patrick Wohlschlegel	Allinea	Yes	Int.
Peter Dueben	University of Oxford	Yes	Ext.
Michael Rezny	Monash University		Ext.
Edouard Audit	CEA	Yes	Ext.
V. Balaji	GFDL, Princeton University	Yes	Ext.
Rupert Ford	STFC Daresbury Laboratory	Yes	Ext.
Jon Rood	ETH Zürich	Yes	Ext.
Valentin Clement	MeteoSwiss	Yes	Ext.
Gilles Civario	Irish Centre for High-End Computing	Yes	Ext.
Carlos Osuna	MeteoSwiss	Yes	Ext.
Aniyan Varghese	EU DG Connect		Ext.
Alison Kennedy	EPCC	Yes	Ext.
Jesu Labarta	BSC	Yes	Ext.

Mark Parsons	EPCC	Yes	Ext.
S. Nishizawa	RIKEN AICS (Japan)	Yes	Ext.
P. Adamidis	DKRZ	Yes	Int.
S. McIntosh-Smith	Univ. Bristol	Yes	Ext.
Oliver Oberst	IBM	Yes	Ext.
M. Schulz	MPI	Yes	Ext.
Sylvie Joussaume	IPSL/CNRS		Int.
Philippe Segers	GENCI		Ext.
Mario Acosta	BSC	Yes	Int.
Peter Fox	Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute		SAB
Michele Weiland	EPCC		SAB
Bryan Lawrence	NCAS, University of Reading	Yes	Int.
Francesca Guglielmo	IPSL		Int.
Paolo Ruti	WWRO		Ext.
Jean-Pierre Panziera	ATOS		Ext.
Malcolm Muggeridge	Seagate		Int.
Steve Mullerworth	MetOffice		Int.
Katerina Goubanova	Cerfacs		Int.
Matthieu Chevallier	CNRM (Meteo-France)		Int..
Orlando Astudillo	LEGOS		Ext.
Giovanni Aloisio	CMCC Foundation		Int.
Silvia Mocavero	CMCC Foundation		Int.
Anke Kamrath	NCAR		Reviewer
Guillaume Alleon	EADS		Reviewer

Computing issues

The first workshop (Lecce) was centred on the then-newly appeared development of innovative dynamical cores, more adapted to the architectures of the most advanced computers. The Toulouse workshop made it possible to review the advancement of a number of these dynamical cores, *e.g.*, ICON, Gung-Ho, Dynamico, ... It was shown that they are now efficient modelling tools, and that they have reached a state of development which makes it possible to implement them in both numerical weather prediction (NWP) and climate models.

The comparison strategy between computing performances of models was discussed in some depth during the third workshop (Hamburg), and general recommendations were put forward. These recommendations have been used to prepare for the CMIP, and they should now be progressively implemented by modelling groups.

A long-standing issue concerns the evolution of future architectures of computers and how these new architectures will/should influence the development of next-generation of weather and climate models. Although all features of this evolution are still not clearly known, some key elements are thought to be unavoidable elements of the future machines: they will be based on manycore and hybrid processors, with memory levels which will require modellers to rethink parts of their codes. At the time of the first workshop the use of GPU had not yet started in climate modelling: a few presentations at the Toulouse workshop showed that this is not the case anymore, and that the speed of computations of realistic models can be already significantly improved. Another interesting suggestion to reduce computing time was also discussed, *i.e.*, use single precision instead of double-precision computations, which should not affect the physical model results.

The necessary refactoring of numerical codes was given a lot of attention and stirred a number of discussions. Various options are still opened, *e.g.*, about the way to deal with concurrency in coupled modelling and/or to parallelize the physics with respect to the dynamics. Another issue is the question of possibly separating the science issues from the HPC optimization: is this separation of concerns feasible? If yes, how could this be done? Could code generation benefit from shared standards, as supported by ESMF in the US? The number of questions to explore is quite large, the gap between actual and future models has never been so important. The community is then faced to efficient coordination and sharing of tasks for preparing efficiently to the forthcoming exascale era.

Data issues

These were first addressed at the second workshop (Toulouse) 3 years before. It has now become very clear that the exabyte challenge is even more crucial than the exaflop one. Some ideas have found their way and are already implemented and used with success, *e.g.*, XIOS. The community nevertheless feels it is just at the start of addressing the data issues: better ways to efficiently process data have still to be explored in a much more detailed and complete manner, and this will require more exchange, and possibly more organization, between the groups.

Foreseen evolution and a few concluding remarks

General concluding remarks may be done concerning the perceived evolution of both the HPC and the community landscapes.

The HPC landscape is continuously evolving, offering ever-increasing peak compute power, but at the expense of additional complexity (concerning both algorithmic solvers and data processing) and changing technical approaches. This is an extremely difficult challenge for NWP and climate modelers. On the one hand it introduces scattering and diversity within the modelling ecosystem, as a number of issues have to be tackled simultaneously. But on the other hand it represents a rare opportunity to develop synergies and to share developments. The collaboration with vendors, which started mostly during the third workshop (Hamburg) eighteen months ago, but was a much more important part of the fourth workshop agenda, is seen as an efficient way to keep increasing the HPC expertise within the modelling community, a necessary step to fully benefit from the next exascale systems.

Finally, ESIWACE offers the opportunity to increase significantly the convergence between NWP and climate modelling. Up to now only the Met Office (UK) and Météo-France (FR) were able to coordinate in-house developments between these two domains, as these establishments are tasked with both applications and are consequently interested in using as much as possible common software elements. The fact that most European national meteorological services are now working within ESIWACE in closer relationship with all European climate modelling centers will increase the exchange of information, will draw attention toward solutions originating from one domain and of likely interest to the other (as it could especially be the case for data issues), and will hopefully lead to common developments. The fifth, already-planned, workshop will likely show progress along these directions.

5. References (*Bibliography*)

André, J.C., G. Aloisio, J. Biercamp, R. Budich, S. Joussaume, B. Lawrence and S. Valcke: High-performance computing for climate modelling. *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, 2014, DOI:10.1175/BAMS-D-00098.1

6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Dissemination

All abstracts and presentations are now freely available on the ESIWACE web site at <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/4th-enes-hpc-workshop/final-agenda-with-abstracts-and-slides>. Jean-Claude André will also coordinate the writing of a summary of the workshop discussions and conclusions with the objective of publishing it in a scientific journal or as a BAMS workshop summary like for the previous HPC workshop.

6.2 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

All the slides presented by the speakers have been collected during the workshop. Some authors made slight changes immediately after the workshop to better reflect the content of their oral presentation. All the slides are now posted on the ESIWACE website and can be downloaded at <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/4th-enes-hpc-workshop/final-agenda-with-abstracts-and-slides>

7. The delivery is delayed

Yes No

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

None

9. Efforts for this deliverable

Person-months spent on this deliverable:

Beneficiary	Person-months	Period covered	Names of scientists involved, including third parties (if appropriate) and their gender (f/m)
DKRZ	0.25	1 Sept.2015-today	Joachim BIERCAMP (m), Project Office
ECMWF	0.25	1 Sept.2015-today	Peter BAUER (m)
MPG	0.25	1 Sept.2015-today	Reinhard BUDICH (m)
CERFACS	1	1 Sept.2015-today	Sophie VALCKE (f), Jean-Claude ANDRE (m)
BSC	0.25	1 Sept.2015-today	Kim SERRADELL (m)
SMHI	0.25	1 Sept.2015-	Uwe FLADRICH (m)

		today	
DWD	0.25	1 Sept.2015- today	Florian PRILL (m)
Total	2.5		

10. Sustainability

10.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

The impetus resulting from the first 3 workshops is still present. It was found that the European scientific community involved in the development and use of meteorological and climate models is always looking for a place to discuss on a regular basis both their results and their projects. Contrarily to what happened in earlier workshops in the HPC series, which were dedicated to the only climate models, the present workshop successfully addressed jointly the two types of models, *i.e.* meteorological and climate. This proved to be fairly simple to organize and interactions naturally took place between the two communities.

10.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

The summary of workshop discussions and conclusions will contribute to update of the ENES infrastructure strategy due before the end of the year in the IS-ENES2 EU project. The outcomes of the workshop will provide inputs for ESIWACE collaboration with the European Extreme Data and Computing Initiative (EXDCI) and with the European Technology Platform for High Performance Computing (ETP4HPC), in particular in the context of the revision of its Strategic Research Agenda.

11. Dissemination activities

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Number	Total funding amount	Type of audience reached In the context of all dissemination & communication activities	Estimated number of persons reached
Organisation of a workshop	1	ca.10.300 Euro	Scientific Community (higher education, Research), Industry	75
Total funding amount		ca 10.300 Euro		

Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

Not applicable.